

Enhancing object-type searches in ESA Astronomy Science Archives extending ESASky AI capabilities with LLM and Retrieval Augmented Generation

M. Doctor^{*1}, M. López-Caniego², F. Marinic³, R. Bhatawdekar³, J. Reerink³

¹Telespazio UK for ESA, Villanueva de la Cañada, E-28692 Madrid, Spain

²Aurora Technology for ESA, Villanueva de la Cañada, E-28692 Madrid, Spain

³European Space Agency, Villanueva de la Cañada, E-28692 Madrid, Spain

Due to the potential of Large Language Models (LLMs) to disrupt the way people interact with information systems across numerous industries, we have investigated options to extend functionality in the context of astronomy science archives. A frequent request by the archive users is to have the ability to search for specific types of objects in archival data, but this information is typically not available given the difficulty of classifying the billions of objects present in astronomical catalogues. In an attempt to address this request by the users, we present a proof of concept implementation aiming to enhance searches in the ESA Astronomy Science Archives. This could be done extending ESASky AI capabilities through the interaction with LLMs and Retrieval Augmented Generation using the information contained in CDS' SIMBAD astronomical object database. The proposed proof of concept already shows that our implementation could offer new capabilities for astronomers when leveraging ESASky for their research.

1 Introduction

Large Language Models (LLMs) without doubt represent one of the most exciting areas in current Artificial Intelligence (AI) research. Since the emergence of ChatGPT [1] in 2022, LLMs have become the foundation for driving innovation in fields like healthcare, finance, science, and more [2] [3] [4].

Astronomical data discovery via advanced querying of the astronomy science archives is a very specialized activity that requires a high level of domain specific knowledge. LLMs' ability to infer information could facilitate these tasks. For example, by analyzing unstructured data such as titles and abstracts from scientific publications, LLMs can provide insights into object classification [5], perform assessments about how to improve queries over tabular data from archives [6],

and assist in new discoveries [7]. Taking advantage of the platform developed in the context of ESA's Virtual Assistant¹ (EVA), and its integration in the ESASky² web application, our proposal explores the possibility of using LLMs to facilitate the exploitation of ESA's astronomy archives in an innovative way.

1.1 EVA: ESA Virtual Assistant Platform

EVA is a web-based platform designed for creating, training, and deploying personalized virtual assistants to enhance ESA services using conversational AI capabilities [8]. These assistants function as software agents that engage users through chat interfaces, enabling genuine conversational interactions delivering valuable assistance or actions [9].

1.2 ESASky

ESASky is a multi-mission, multi-wavelength, and multi-messenger web application that allow users to discover a large number of data sets. ESASky takes advantage of Virtual Observatory protocols to communicate with the Astronomy Science archives located at ESA as well as with other external data centres across the world to search in real time for information about the observations, catalogues and spectral data available in a given region of the sky (see Figure 1).

ESASky also offers users the possibility to discover the data contents of the astronomy archives using Natural Language Processing (NLP) via the EVA platform. The EVA bot in ESASky translates the interactions from the users into Application Programming Interface (API) commands. However, there are limitations to this pre-LLMs technology, leaving room for improvement in the way users interact with the bot.

¹<https://eva.esa.int>

²<https://sky.esa.int>

*Corresponding author. E-Mail:miguel.doctor@ext.esa.int

Figure 1: ESASky user interface

2 LLM-RAG Architecture

LLMs are already producing excellent results on multiple NLP tasks, often without specific prompts. Nevertheless, their performance in handling domain-specific data is still limited due to missing information during training, the challenges incorporating new knowledge, and occurrences of "hallucinations" [10]. In order to overcome these issues, we propose applying a Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) architecture [11] consisting of several components, including prompt template definition [2], semantic classifiers on titles and abstracts, and tabular data handling [5]. RAG processes operates on the premise that while LLMs are general in nature, they can be directed towards producing domain-specific answers by providing appropriate context in the prompts.

2.1 LLM-RAG in ESASky

In the context of the EVA virtual assistant in ESASky, we want to go one step beyond and use LLMs to improve on the interactions between the users and the web application. Furthermore, we want to explore the possibility of using RAG to enhance the response from the LLM with astronomical information obtained from the SIMBAD Astronomical Object Database³ created and maintained by the Strasbourg astronomy Data Center. The SIMBAD database provides tabular information about billions of objects studied in the scientific literature in the last century,

³<https://simbad.cds.unistra.fr/simbad/>

including coordinates in the sky and in some cases object type (e.g., star, galaxy, nebula, etc.). In this work, we want to take advantage of the ability of LLMs to infer information from the titles and abstracts from scientific publications to guess the object type when not available. In particular, we want to allow users to search for specific types of objects in a given region of the sky using SIMBAD, even when the object type column is not populated.

With this goal in mind, we have tested how LLM + RAG based on SIMBAD data in a given region of the sky can allow us to make the connection between coordinates of an object in the sky and object type.

2.2 RAG Pipeline Implementation

The approach outlined in this paper focuses on a RAG pipeline crafted to process and evaluate question-answer pairs for extracting domain-specific knowledge over SIMBAD data tables. The proposed pipeline is shown in Figure 2. The RAG process is divided into 2 distinct stages: *Data indexing* and *Context Retrieval*.

2.2.1 Data Indexing

The *Data Indexing* phase aims to gather a working dataset, including sourcing data mainly from SIMBAD astronomical object database. During the indexing stage, SIMBAD tables are pre-processed in a way that enables efficient search during the *Context Retrieval stage*. This process involves performing several tasks over SIMBAD such as data reformatting, mapping rows by sentences/paragraphs, chunking, embedding and storing into a vector database. This stage

Figure 2: RAG Pipeline

is typically performed offline, so the relevant SIMBAD catalogues are pre-loaded and the users do not need to wait for this process to be completed. A simplified representation of this stage is shown in Figure 2 making use of solid arrows. On top of the diagram we see how SIMBAD catalogues are converted to embeddings and stored into a vector database.

2.2.2 Context Retrieval

The *Context Retrieval* stage occurs online, and it is triggered when a user submits a question that should be answered using the indexed content. This stage is also illustrated in Figure 2, but its flow is represented using dashed arrows. The user input involves a question about any astronomical object type previously loaded in the *Data Indexing* phase. The user question is moved towards two different components.

1. **Embeddings Model:** The objective here is to extract the related information from the collected documents using the user input. The question text is transformed into embeddings and passed to the vector database to perform a cosine similarity search over the stored data. The produced output containing the best candidates fragments of content is the *Retrieval Context*.
2. **Prompt Manager:** The prompt manager handles the two different prompt templates defined for this RAG pipeline. At this point, the prompt manager takes the user question as text and combine it with the first template, the *Classifier Template*.

This template instructs the LLM to perform a classification task over the *Retrieval Context*.

The next step is the generation of the final *Classifier Prompt*, which is produced combining the *User Question*, *Template Classifier* and the *Retrieval Context*. Once crafted, the prompt is sent to the *EVA-LLM*. The *EVA-LLM* module is offered by EVA platform. Our setup makes use of a mistral-7B parameter model with GGUF 4-bit quantization, a configuration that provides a good balance between computational efficiency and performance. The processing step is crucial as it involves parsing unstructured data (titles and abstracts) contained in tabular data (SIMBAD entries). The LLM applies the classification and filtering operations and returns those SIMBAD entries that might be related to the object type requested by the user.

Finally, the output (consisting of a list of filtered candidates returned by *EVA-LLM*) is sent back to the *Prompt Manager*. The *Prompt Manager* takes this output and the second template, the *Coordinate Extractor Template*, and produces the *Coordinates Prompt*, which takes care of finding the coordinates related to the filtered candidate objects. Hence, this prompt is passed on to *EVA-LLM* for processing. The LLM generates the output including the candidate objects along with their coordinates. This information formatted in JSON is offered back to the user in order to allow ESASky to navigate to the relevant area.

3 Results

We have validated our RAG pipeline using a small control dataset obtained from SIMBAD⁴ using the following query:

```
SELECT TOP 1000
otype, ra, dec, title, abstract
FROM "public".basic b
JOIN "public".ref r ON (b.oid=r.oidbib)
WHERE r.abstract LIKE '%a%'
AND r.abstract NOT LIKE 'Abstract only'.
```

As a result, we obtain a table with 770 rows with object type, coordinates, title and abstract, that we use to validate the pipeline. First, we focus on a subset of 10 entries selected to cover different topics in astronomy (dark matter, active galactic nuclei, far infrared astronomy and variable stars). We have used these 10 entries as input to the RAG, and we have validated the responses one by one to confirm that the text used to prompt the LLM was not present, or only partially present, in the titles and abstracts. Second, we have repeated the same test but using in the RAG all the results from the query. We used the same prompts for the categories mentioned above, and confirmed that with a much larger RAG the LLM gave the same results for the same subset. This confirms that the LLM is behaving as expected, producing the same results for the same prompts for the same subset of SIMBAD rows, and additional results that we are not validating in this work but that are potentially correct.

For this prototype, we have simplified the dataset selecting only a few relevant columns from the SIMBAD tables: *object type*, *right ascension*, *declination*, *abstract* and *publication title*. In our tested question (*Can you provide the coordinates for possible observations related to «astronomical category?»*), the LLM showed a very poor performance when applying zero-shot or few-shot techniques. Table 1 shows the percentage of the samples within our small dataset (10 rows) returning a valid set of coordinates for each requested astronomical object. In most of the cases using zero-shot approach, the model "hallucinates" and provides non-existing coordinates with a slight improvement when using few-shot technique. In addition, in those samples where the returned coordinates are valid, we have detected that in several cases they are not actually related to the astronomical object included in the question. These results are expected and compatible with the fact, that the LLM has not been specifically trained on SIMBAD data, so it presents a lack of knowledge about SIMBAD catalogues and the way to interpret its content. However, the execution of the two steps RAG

pipeline described in this article reveals very promising results. First, the classification step helps us to identify the entries related to the topic requested by the user, reducing the risk of obtaining valid but non-related coordinates. Then, the second step guarantees that the set of coordinates returned by the LLM is real and it can be found in the context mitigating possible hallucinations. Also, our approach worked out for those entries where the object type was missing in the catalogue, so the inference mechanism over titles and abstracts produced valuable insights in order to fulfill incomplete information within the catalogue.

Prompt Category	Zero-shot	Few-shot	RAG
Dark Matter	1/3	1/3	3/3
AGN	1/2	1/2	2/2
FIR	0/2	0/2	2/2
Variable Star	1/5	2/5	4/5

Table 1: Experimental results using the control dataset (10 entries). For each prompt category we have performed three tests using a different technique; zero-shot, few-shot and our 2 steps RAG pipeline. The values displayed in the cells represent the number of good results over the total of positive matches. Note that in two cases there is a good fit for more than one category, which explains that the sum up of the total matches is 12 with a dataset of 10 entries.

As an example, these are the prompts used for each step in the RAG pipeline when applying to the prompt category Dark Matter.

1. Classifier Prompt.

Role: You are a helpful AI assistant expert in astrophysics with data analysis skills, expert on CSV files and tabular data.

Context: Consider the following knowledge base ```-context-``` in order to provide a proper and accurate answer.

Source: You are provided below with a CSV table delimited by triple backticks with observations with the following columns: 'otype', 'ra', 'dec', 'title', 'abstract'.

Goal: Your goal is to determine if a provided set of scientific titles and abstracts are related to a specific topic in the astronomy field.

⁴<https://simbad.cds.unistra.fr/simbad/sim-tap/>

Here is the topic in astronomy:
````-Prompt_category: Dark Matter-````

The list of abstracts to analyze are indicated as follows and delimited by triple backticks:

Abstract list:  
````-abstract_list-````

Reply providing a CSV table with the same columns than the source (otype,ra,dec,title,abstract).

One for each abstract. Do not add any extra explanation to the answer.

2. Coordinates Prompt.

Role: You are a helpful AI assistant expert in data analysis with a strong background processing CSV files and tabular data.

Source: You are provided below with a CSV table delimited by triple backticks with observations with the following columns:
`'otype','ra','dec','title','abstract'.`

Goal: Your task is to return a list of JSON objects, one per row with 3 keys each: `'title','ra','dec'`.

The objects must fill in the `'title','ra'` and `'dec'` keys taken directly from the respective columns of the CSV file.

The table is below, delimited by triple backticks.

Table:
`...`

`-csv_table_filtered_rows-`
`...`

Do not make up any value in the JSON object. For each title, the values ra,dec are the ones from the same row. Reply just the JSON object without any extra comment or explanation.

4 Discussion

In this work we show that LLMs perform well in inferring information from astronomical publications thanks to RAG architecture, even though they have not been specifically trained on the domain. The proof of concept presented here is very promising and has helped us to validate our proposal. Nevertheless, there are limitations to overcome in order to be able to include this feature as a production ready service within ESASky as follows:

- We have fully validated the results from the pipeline using for the RAG a small subset of the SIMBAD table. We have also checked that these results are still valid when using for the RAG the full table of 770 entries. However, the additional results produced by the LLM when using the extended RAG input, that are potentially useful, would benefit from some automatic validation process. For this, some acceptance criteria should be defined, for example, the level of accuracy acceptable by the user.
- The execution of the presented RAG pipeline significantly reduced the risk of hallucination, although it is not totally removed. Therefore, we plan to introduce a self-correction mechanism relying on Chain-of-Thoughts [12] and agentic design patterns [13] to guarantee all returned coordinates are valid.
- Response times have been kept under acceptable levels during our experimentation due to the use of a small size SIMBAD catalogue. When scaling it up, we must evolve the current architecture in order to allow running the *Data Indexing* phase as per user request needs. Possible alternatives are being discussed with the Data Science team at ESAC to take advantage of the GPU capabilities of ESA Datalabs.
- Converting rows from tabular data into natural language descriptions has demonstrated to increase the accuracy of the LLM predictions [5]. Consequently, we propose to add this processing to our *Data Indexing* phase in order to improve our results.

5 Acknowledgements

We would like to acknowledge the Data Science and Archives Division at the European Space Astronomy Center (ESAC), the ESAC Science Data Centre, the Science Programmatic IT team and the ESA Datalabs

team, for supporting this project in the context of the Large Language Models working group activities at ESAC. This research has made use of the SIMBAD database, operated at CDS, Strasbourg, France.

References

1. Ray, P. P. ChatGPT: A comprehensive review on background, applications, key challenges, bias, ethics, limitations and future scope. *Internet of Things and Cyber-Physical Systems* **3**, 121–154. issn: 2667-3452. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S266734522300024X> (2023).
2. Brown, T. *et al.* Language models are few-shot learners. *Advances in neural information processing systems* **33**, 1877–1901 (2020).
3. Biswas, S. Prospective role of chat gpt in the military: According to chatgpt. *Qeios* (2023).
4. Zhao, H. *et al.* Revolutionizing finance with llms: An overview of applications and insights. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2401.11641* (2024).
5. Hegselmann, S. *et al.* Tabllm: Few-shot classification of tabular data with large language models in *International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Statistics* (2023), 5549–5581.
6. Chen, X., Wang, T., Qiu, T., Qin, J. & Yang, M. *Open-SQL Framework: Enhancing Text-to-SQL on Open-source Large Language Models* 2024. arXiv: 2405.06674 [cs.CL].
7. Romera-Paredes, B. *et al.* Mathematical discoveries from program search with large language models. *Nature* **625**, 468–475. issn: 1476-4687. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06924-6> (Jan. 2024).
8. Doctor, M. *EVA (ESA Virtual Assistant): The conversational AI platform for Space* version 1. May 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6557014>.
9. López-Caniego, M. & Doctor, M. *ESA Virtual Assistant in ESASky: enabling archival data exploration via natural language processing* May 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6566293>.
10. Ji, Z. *et al.* Survey of hallucination in natural language generation. *ACM Computing Surveys* **55**, 1–38 (2023).
11. Lewis, P. *et al.* Retrieval-augmented generation for knowledge-intensive nlp tasks. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* **33**, 9459–9474 (2020).
12. Wei, J. *et al.* Chain of Thought Prompting Elicits Reasoning in Large Language Models. *ArXiv abs/2201.11903*. <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:246411621> (2022).
13. Gou, Z. *et al.* CRITIC: Large Language Models Can Self-Correct with Tool-Interactive Critiquing 2024. arXiv: 2305.11738 [cs.CL].